

Non-Destructive Testing Method of Fiber Orientation and Fiber Content in FRP Using Microwave

K. Urabe, S. Yomoda

Industrial Products Research Institute, AIST, MITI, 1-1-4 Higashi, Yatabe-machi, Tsukuba-gun, Ibaraki 305, Japan

ABSTRACT

A new non-destructive testing method of measuring the fiber orientation as well as the fiber content in FRP is devised using 4GHz microwave. Experiments are carried out on unidirectional CFRP, CFRP in which some of the fiber has different orientation, and unidirectional GFRP. Fiber content of unidirectional CFRP is evaluated by reflection measurement, but as the fiber content increases, the change in the reflectance decreases. Fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP and GFRP is detected both by the reflection measurement and by the measurement of cross polarization components of transmitted wave. The sensitivity of the measurement is much higher in case of CFRP than that of GFRP. The measurement of the ratio of two components make it possible to evaluate the fiber direction, independently of the fiber content, within certain angle region. Some theoretical calculations are performed on unidirectional samples and agree fairly well with the experiments. Misorientation of fiber is also detected by the present method.

INTRODUCTION

It is required to develop non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques for detecting defects with high accuracy in order to improve the reliability of fiber reinforced composites. Various kinds of NDT techniques have been studied by several workers, such as ultrasonics (1)(2), X-ray (1)(3), electromagnetic wave (2)(4)(6), eddy current (1)(5), and acoustic emission(1). Among these various techniques, the one using microwave, electromagnetic wave of high frequency, is applicable to evaluate fiber content, fiber orientation, moisture content, curing of resin, air void content, and thickness of FRP, and some experiments have been reported (2)(4)(6) which are applied mainly to GFRP. In case of CFRP, which is recently important material for aircrafts, carbon fiber in CFRP may produce strong effect for microwave because of its electric conductivity. Thus the microwave technique can become a powerful NDT technique for evaluating fiber content and fiber orientation in CFRP, which have an effect to its strength and dynamical properties. In this paper, a measuring apparatus using 4GHz microwave is devised, by which measurements of reflectance and cross polarization components of transmitted wave are performed. Measurements of fiber content and fiber orientation are made using this apparatus about unidirectional CFRP, CFRP in which some of the fiber has different orientation, and unidirectional GFRP.

Fig.1. Schematic illustration of apparatus for the measurements.
 Att.:Variable attenuator. R-C trans.:Rectangular-circular transducer.
 S.W.R.:Standing wave ratio measuring equipment. T.:Magic tee.

Fig.1 shows the outline of the testing apparatus devised and used in the present work. Most parts of the apparatus are commercial microwave components for 4GHz. Although omitted in the figure, some isolators are used where necessary. Microwave generated by a signal generator (S.G.), frequency 4GHz and maximum power 1mW, is transmitted in a rectangular waveguide (58.1x29.1mm) as TE₀₁ mode in which the polarization of the electromagnetic wave is parallel to the shorter sides of the waveguide as shown in Fig.1. After twisting the polarization of the wave to 45° direction, the waveguide is transformed into a circular one (54.0mm in diameter), where the TE₀₁ mode of rectangular waveguide changes to TE₁₁ mode of circular one. Then the wave propagates into the sample which is inserted in the circular waveguide. Part of the incident wave is reflected and absorbed by the sample, and the remainder passes through. The reflectance and the transmittance depend on dielectric constant, electric conductivity, and thickness of the sample. The TE₁₁ mode in the circular waveguide can be separated into two cross polarized components: a vertical component, E_v, and a horizontal one, E_h. These components of the transmitted wave are separately transmitted into two rectangular waveguides, using a polarization coupler. They are guided to the terminal ① and ②, respectively, of the magic tee after passing through the attenuator and the phase shifter, as shown in Fig.1. Then the electric field of the wave at the terminal ④, E₄, is equal to E_v-E_h, whose amplitude can be detected as D.C. voltage output of a crystal detector.

Unidirectional FRP can be treated as a electrically anisotropic material whose one of the principal axes coincides with the fiber direction, because the electric properties of the fiber is different from that of the matrix resin. Assuming that the attenuators and the phase shifter has been adjusted so that the output of the detector of the magic tee is zero before inserting the sample, then E₄ is expressed as follows;

$$\dot{E}_4 = (\dot{t}_1 - \dot{t}_2) \cos 2\theta \dot{t}_{h0} \dot{E}_{hi} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{t}_1 and \dot{t}_2 are the transmittances of the sample for the polarization parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction, respectively, θ is the angle between E_v and the fiber direction as shown in Fig.2, \dot{t}_{h0} represents attenuation and phase change of E_h while passing from the polarization coupler to the terminal ② of the magic tee, and \dot{E}_{hi} is the horizontal component of the incident wave. |E₄| is measured as D.C. voltage output of the crystal detector, thus |t₁-t₂| or θ is evaluated.

The amplitude ratio and the phase difference between the two cross components of transmitted wave, which is expressed

Fig.2. Fiber direction relative to polarization of wave in cross section of waveguide.

$$\frac{\dot{E}_v}{\dot{E}_h} = \frac{\dot{r}_1 \cos^2 \theta + \dot{r}_2 \sin^2 \theta + (\dot{r}_1 - \dot{r}_2) \sin \theta \cos \theta}{\dot{r}_1 \sin^2 \theta + \dot{r}_2 \cos^2 \theta + (\dot{r}_1 - \dot{r}_2) \sin \theta \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

is also measured by adjusting the attenuators and the phase shifter so that the output of the detector is zero after inserting the sample.

On the other hand, reflectance of the sample, $|\dot{r}|$, is obtained by measuring the ratio between the maximum and the minimum of the standing wave which occurs by an interference of the reflected wave with the incident one. In case of a unidirectional sample, the relation between the reflectance and the direction of fiber is as follows;

$$\dot{r} = \dot{r}_1 \cos^2 \theta + \dot{r}_2 \sin^2 \theta \quad (3)$$

where \dot{r}_1 and \dot{r}_2 are the reflectances of the wave whose polarization is parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction, respectively, and θ is the angle between the polarization of wave and the fiber direction.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sample

CFRP prepreg laminated samples were prepared by laminating 2 \bar{v} 8 prepreg sheet layers of "Torayca type S305", 0.25mm in thickness, and curing them by a hotpress of pressure 50kgf/cm² (4.9MPa), for 1 hour at 120°C, and for 2 hours at 130°C. Some of the samples were prepared so that part of the layers have different fiber orientation. Cloth laminated samples were prepared by laminating "Torayca cloth #6105" or "Torayca cloth #6103" with epoxy resin, "Epikote 828", by hand lay-up method, curing under normal temperature and pressure, and aftercuring at 120°C for 2 hours. 4 \bar{v} 7 layers of cloth were laminated, and in some of the samples part of the fibers were pulled away on purpose to vary fiber content. GFRP samples were prepared by hand winding of glass fiber, "Nittobo roving strand RS240", with epoxy resin, "Epikote 828". The samples were cut into discs of 54mm in diameter, inserted in the circular waveguide, and used for experiments. Fiber contents of the prepreg laminated samples and GFRP samples were measured by burning matrix resin out, and those of the cloth laminated samples were calculated from the number of laminated cloths and fiber density in the cloths which were used to make each sample.

Reflection Measurements

Reflectance is obtained by measuring standing wave ratio. The carbon fiber in CFRP may produce much greater influence to microwave compared with the epoxy resin matrix because of its electric conductivity. Therefore reflection as well as transmission of microwave depends directly on fiber content in the area where the wave propagates. Fig.3 shows the relationship between fiber content (per unit area) of unidirectional CFRP samples

Fig.3. Relation between reflectance and fiber content of unidirectional CFRP.

Fig.4. Relation between reflectance and fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP. (Lines:calculated values by eq. (3), V_f :Fiber volume fraction, d :Thickness of sample.)

and measured reflectance. The polarization of incident wave is perpendicular to fiber direction in Fig.3. As shown in Fig.4, the dependence of reflectance on fiber content is strongest in this direction. When fiber content is low, the change in reflectance with the change in fiber content is relatively high. So it is easy to detect the change of fiber content from reflection measurement. But it becomes difficult to detect the change when fiber content is more than about 100mg/cm² (fiber volume fraction $V_f > 56\%$ when thickness $d=1.0\text{mm}$) because the change in reflectance decreases. Fig.4 shows the relationship between fiber direction in unidirectional CFRP samples and reflectance. Lines in the figure are calculated values using equation (3). The measured reflectance values at 0° and 90° are used in the calculation as \hat{r}_1 and \hat{r}_2 , respectively. The agreements are fairly well. The sensitivity of detecting the change in fiber direction is the highest at an angle of 45°, and it becomes higher as fiber content becomes lower. The value of reflectance does not depend on fiber content when the fiber is parallel to the polarization of the wave, but dependence appears as the angle increases, and becomes maximum at 90°, where the fiber is perpendicular to the electric field polarization.

Experiments were also carried out on CFRP samples in which some of the fiber had different orientation. Fig.5 shows the result when central 1 layer out of 5 layers of prepreg has different orientation. When the misorientation of one layer is more than 20°, the reflectance is almost constant like an isotropic sample. Fig.6 shows effects of location of the misoriented layer. The fiber near surface has greater influence, and when the layer with different orientation is inside of the sample, the difference between maximum and minimum of the reflectance becomes smaller and the curve resembles to symmetrical shape.

The measurement and the calculation were also carried out on a few unidirectional CFRP samples. The result is shown in Fig.7. The lines in the figure represent calculated values from the complex dielectric constants which were measured using rectangular waveguide at the same frequency. The real part of the dielectric constant for the polarization along the fiber direction is larger than that for the polarization perpendicular to it, and the higher the fiber content, the larger the dielectric constant. These are because the dielectric constant of glass, 5.1 at 10GHz, is larger than that of epoxy, 2.9 at 4GHz. The change in reflectance is much smaller comparing with that of CFRP, because the difference in the characteristics between glass and epoxy is smaller than

Fig.5. Relation between reflectance and fiber direction of CFRP when central 1 layer out of 5 layers has different orientation. (Solid line:calculated by eq.(3).) [Fiber content:138mg/cm², $V_f=53\%$.]

Fig.6. Relation between reflectance and fiber direction of CFRP when 1 layer out of 4 layers has different orientation. (Solid line:calculated by eq.(3).) [Fiber content:108mg/cm², $V_f=55\%$.]

that between carbon and epoxy.

Measurements of Cross Polarization Components

Fig. 8. shows the relation between $|\dot{E}_4| = |\dot{E}_v - \dot{E}_h|$, which is the electric field strength at the terminal ④ of the magic tee, and fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP samples. $|\dot{E}_4|$ is normalized by the electric field strength of the horizontal component of the incident wave, $|\dot{E}_{hi}|$. As shown in Fig. 1, the angle between the polarization of incident wave and that of E_v is 45° . Thus, 0° direction in Fig. 4 \sim 7 corresponds to 45° direction in Fig. 8 and Fig. 10 \sim 13 which will be shown later. The lines in Fig. 8 represents calculated value from equation (1) using the average of the measured values of $|\dot{E}_4|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$ at 0° and 90° , which are the maximum value. The agreement is pretty well. The crystal detector and the D.C. volt meter are enough sensitive to be able to detect 0.2% change of $|\dot{E}_4|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$, so change of 1° in fiber direction is detectable. Comparing Fig. 8 with Fig. 4, the sensitivity of detection is highest at 45° and 135° , which correspond to 0° and 90° , respectively, in Fig. 4. This is just opposite to the reflection measurement, Fig. 4.

$|\dot{E}_4|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$ has maximum value at 0° , 90° , and 180° , and according to equation (4), the maximum value, $|\dot{E}_{4max}|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$, is proportional to $|\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2|$. So $|\dot{E}_{4max}|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$ is expected to depend on fiber content. Fig. 9 is the plot of $|\dot{E}_{4max}|/|\dot{E}_{hi}|$ vs. fiber content. $|\dot{E}_{4max}|$ decreases as fiber content increases, but the dispersion of the measured values is broader than the reflection measurement.

Fig. 10 shows the relation between fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP and strength ratio of the two cross components, $|\dot{E}_v|/|\dot{E}_h|$. The lines in the figures are calculated from equation (2) using the values at 0° and 90° . In Fig. 10, the calculated lines and the measured points of all samples in the angle region between 115° to 155° overlap almost on one line within 1dB, independently of fiber content. Therefore it is possible to detect fiber direction, independently of fiber

Fig. 7. Relation between reflectance and fiber direction of unidirectional GFRP. (Solid lines:calculated from dielectric constants and eq. (3).)

V_f :Fiber volume fraction, d :Thickness of sample, ϵ_1, ϵ_2 :Dielectric constants of parallel and perpendicular to fiber direction, respectively.

Fig. 8. Relation between $|\dot{E}_4|$ and fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP.

(Solid lines:calculated by eq. (1).)
[Samples are the same ones as Fig. 10.]

Fig. 9. Plot of maximum of $|\dot{E}_4|$ versus fiber content of unidirectional CFRP.

content, with accuracy of about 3° in this region. And if the measurement of cross polarization ratio is carried out together with that of reflectance which is shown in Fig.4, it is possible to detect separately fiber direction and fiber content of a unidirectional CFRP without rotating the sample or the polarization in the angle region above mentioned, which corresponds to $90^\circ \pm 20^\circ$ in Fig.4. The phase difference is also measured, but it varies little with the change of angle in the above region.

The maximum values of the strength ratio and the phase difference are not located at the angle where the polarization of E_v or E_h coincides to the principal axis. These maximum values have a tendency to be smaller for the prepreg laminated samples whose fiber content is higher comparing with the cloth laminated samples. However, no apparent dependence on fiber content as the reflectance and $|E_4|$ is found.

The same experiment was carried out about prepreg laminated CFRP samples in which some of the fiber has different orientation. Fig. 11 is the result of measurement of $|E_4|$ when central 1 layer out of 5 layers of laminated prepreg has different orientation. The solid lines in Fig.11 are calculated values from equation (1), which agree with the measured values even in case of the samples with 5° , 11° , or 22° misoriented layer. This means that it is difficult by the measurement of $|E_4|$ to distinguish a sample with misorientation in its central layer from a sample with higher fiber content and no misorientation. From the measurement of the strength ratio $|E_v|/|E_h|$, it is shown that difference of the measured strength ratio curve between the misoriented sample and the unidirectional sample becomes apparent when the misorientation of central one layer is

Fig.10. Relation between electric field strength ratio of two cross components and fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP. (Lines indicate calculated values by eq.(2).) V_f :Fiber volume fraction, d :Thickness of sample.

Fig.11. Relation between $|E_4|$ and fiber direction of CFRP when center 1 layer out of 5 layers has different orientation. (Solid lines:calculated by eq. (1).) [Fiber content:138mg/cm², $V_f=53\%$.]

Fig.12. Relation between $|E_4|$ and fiber direction of CFRP when 1 layer out of 4 layers has different orientation. (Solid line:calculated by eq. (1).) [Fiber content:108mg/cm², $V_f=55\%$.]

more than 20°.

Fig.12 shows the effect of location of the misoriented layer. The value of $|\dot{E}_{4\max}|$ is smaller and the curves resemble to symmetrical shape when the mis-oriented layer is located rather inside of the sample. In addition, it is remarkable that the curve of the 1st layer misoriented sample is almost the same shape as 90° shifted curve of the 4th layer misoriented one. From the measurement of $|\dot{E}_V|/|\dot{E}_H|$, it is shown that 3rd or 4th misoriented layer exert greater influence, which is the opposite result to the reflection measurement.

The measurements and calculations of \dot{E}_V/\dot{E}_H were also performed on unidirectional GFRP samples. Fig.13 is the results of strength ratio, $|\dot{E}_V|/|\dot{E}_H|$, and phase difference, $\phi_h - \phi_v$, together. The calculations are carried out using the measured dielectric constants. The measured values agree well with the calculated ones, but the sensitivity of the measurement is much lower than that of CFRP. The reason might be the same as what has been mentioned in the end of the reflection measurement.

CONCLUSION

A non-destructive testing apparatus for measuring fiber orientation and fiber content was devised using microwave of 4GHz. Experiments were carried out on CFRP and GFRP samples. Results are summarized as follows.

- 1) Fiber content of unidirectional CFRP sample is detected by the reflection measurement. As the fiber content increases, the change of the reflectance decreases, and it is difficult to detect the change of fiber content when it is more than 100mg/cm².
- 2) Fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP is also detected by the reflection measurement whose sensitivity is maximum when the fiber direction is at 45° angle to the polarization of the wave, and it decreases as the fiber content increases.
- 3) Fiber direction in unidirectional CFRP is detected with higher sensitivity by measuring the difference and the ratio between two cross polarization components of the transmitted wave. In case of the measurement of the difference between the two components, the sensitivity is highest when the fiber direction is at 0° and 90° angle to the polarization of the wave, which is the opposite to the result of the reflection measurement. The measurement of the ratio of the two components make it possible to detect the fiber direction, independently of the fiber content, when the fiber direction is between 70° and 110° to the polarization of the incident wave.
- 4) The experimental results agree well with the calculation treating the fiber direction of unidirectional CFRP as one of the electric principal axes.
- 5) Misorientation of fiber is also detected by this method. The measured values depend on the location of the misoriented layer as well as the angle of the mis-orientation. When the misoriented layer is located near the center of the

Fig.13. Relation between ratio of two cross polarizations and fiber direction of unidirectional GFRP. $|\dot{E}_V|/|\dot{E}_H|$: Electric field strength ratio. $\phi_h - \phi_v$: Phase difference.

(Lines:calculated from dielectric constants and equation (2).)

V_f :Fiber volume fraction, d :Thickness of sample, ϵ_1, ϵ_2 :Dielectric constants of parallel and perpendicular to fiber direction, respectively.

sample, the shape of the curve is similar to that of the unidirectional sample with higher fiber content.

6) Experiments and theoretical calculation are also performed on unidirectional GFRP samples. The agreement is fairly well, but the sensitivity of the measurement is much lower than that of CFRP.

REFERENCE

1. Prakash,R., "Non-destructive testing of composites", *Composites*, Vol.11, No.4, 1980, pp.217-224.
2. Yomoda,S., "Non-destructive measurement of fiber content in FRP", *Proceedings of the 2nd Japan-USSR Symposium on Composite Materials*, 1980, pp.159-167.
3. Prakash,R., "Fibre volume fraction measurement in composites by X-ray diffractometer", *Composites*, Vol.12, No.3, 1981, pp.193-194.
4. Umeda,T., Miyashita,T. and Kako,Y., "New evaluation method of dielectric materials using a microwave technique", *IEEE Transactions on Electrical Insulation*, Vol.EI-15, No.4, 1980, pp.340-349.
5. Prakash,R. and Owston,C.N., "Eddy-current method for the determination of lay-up order in cross-plyed cfrp laminates", *Composites*, Vol.7, No.2, 1976, pp.88-92.
6. Hendron,J.A., Groble,K.K., Gruetzmacher,R.W., McClurg,G.O. and Retsky,M.W., "Corona and microwave methods for the detection of voids in glass-epoxy structures", *Material Evaluation*, Vol.XXII, No7, 1964, pp.311-314.